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ALGORITHMS AND HARDWARE AND SOFTWARE SUPPORT FOR IMPROVING ENERGY EFFICIENCY IN TELECOMMUNICATIONS FACILITIES BASED ON DIGITAL TECHNOLOGIES

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KEYWORDS

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ABSTRACT

In this article, researches are carried out on the processes of increasing the efficiency of electric energy sources and changing their magnitudes to secondary signals, calculation of multi-parameter converters of measurement and control in energy supply processes. Information is provided on the wide use of digital technologies and their modern hardware and software tools in improving energy efficiency, the principles of monitoring with their help, the principles of structure, models and algorithms of processing and transmitting devices on a corresponding basis.

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Introduction

The widespread use of various signal converters for the distribution of information to increase the efficiency of energy supply sources in the world, devices and devices that provide signals to ensure continuous and high-quality operation of energy supply systems in the implementation of continuous control processes with their help, tools, and a number of scientific research works aimed at improving algorithms and software tools are being carried out. Special attention is paid to planning, development of software tools and technical solutions based on the monitoring of the power of sources of the quantity and quality of energy produced in order to ensure the reliable operation of the energy supply system. At the same time, the construction principles of devices for changing the size and parameters of electrical energy sources into secondary signals and the creation of their software tools are considered urgent issues. [1-3].

In the remote monitoring of energy supply sources, the signal transmission unit performs the main task of transmitting information about the current state of energy supply sources to the system monitoring program in multi-parameter signal change processes. The structure of the converter of the primary currents of energy sources into a signal is selected taking into account the structural characteristics of the current transfer device located on a magnetic base. In the monitoring of energy supply devices, Arduino and STM32 microcontrollers were compared and the most optimal was selected, mainly in the state of changes in the device's operation and in its control [1; 2-163-p, 38-p].

Measuring and control instruments elements of PCU intended for both continuous and periodic monitoring of the electricity quality should have sufficient non-volatile memory in volume, allowing long-term storage of measurement results. The archives with the results of the control, accumulated in the memory, should contain information about the time measurements.

These archives can't be adjusted and are the most reliable sources of information about the measurements were taken. Currently, there are several approaches to ensure long-term storage of measurement and control results [2].

The information displayed on the displays without additional processing of the measurement and control results, should reflect all the characteristics of the electric power quality that determine the conditions for fulfilling or not meeting the requirements for a given time interval during which these characteristics are obtained, as well as extreme values of the measured parameters in this interval [3].

The structure of a typical means of measuring and control the quality of electric energy on the basis of PCD is given in fig.1

Fig. 1. Functional modules of hardware for remote monitoring of energy supply facilities.

The structure of measuring and control instruments:

BLT - a block of large-scale transformations;

BADC - block of analog-to-digital converter;

IPU - information-processing unit;

RAM - random access memory;

CPU - central processing unit;

ROM - read-only memory;

NVM - non-volatile memory;

DT - display tool;

CI - communication interface;

AD - alphanumeric display.

The structure of the process current monitoring device of energy supply management devices is presented in Fig. 2. The device has a separate connection tool for each source for remote monitoring of energy supply processes of computing and information communication complexes. In monitoring and controlling the state of the source, it processes the commands coming from the software complex and performs the processes of connecting and disconnecting the necessary power supply sources.

Fig. 2. The structure of the energy efficiency monitoring device in the power supply system.

METHODOLOGY

Modelling of signal conversion processes in elements of PCD

A reliable assessment of electric power quality indicators (PQI) in the nets and the development of effective measures aimed at ensuring electric power quality are impossible without instrumental control. To carry out such control, specialized measuring instruments (SMI) are required. Intensive development of microprocessor technology has allowed domestic developers to create multifunctional SMI, designed to control and analyze the quality of electricity. The tasks of power quality control determine the specific requirements for PCD [3].

The only condition when choosing a SMI is that all means must comply with the requirements of GOST 13109-97 [3]. In part regarding the measurement and control algorithms of the PQI and the permissible measurement errors. The list of measured PQI is established by GOST 13109-97, but can be expanded depending on the tasks to be solved. Graph model of the signal conversion process in PCD given in fig. 3

Fig. 3 Graph model of the signal conversion process.

On the basis of graph model determining the parameters and values of conversion processes of PCD [1]:

$$U_{BTL} = K_a U_a = K_b U_b = K_c U_c = K_A I_A = K_B I_B = K_C I_C = K_{M1} U_{KPS}; \quad (1)$$

$$U_{BADC} = K_{Ue} U_{BTL} = K_{Ie} U_{BTL} = K_{M2} U_{KPS}; \quad (2)$$

$$U_{IPU} = K_{M3} U_{KPS} + K_{C1} U_{BADC} + (K_{C5} - K_{C4}) U_K; \quad (3)$$

$$U_{NVM} = K_{C2} U_{IPU}; \quad (4)$$

$$U_{DT} = K_{C3} U_{IPU}; \quad (5)$$

$$U_{CI} = K_{C4} U_{IPU}; \quad (6)$$

$$(7) \quad \frac{U_{IPU} - U_{KPS}}{K_{M3}} + \frac{U_{IPU} - U_{BADC}}{K_{C3}} + \frac{U_{IPU} - U_K}{K_{C5}} = K_{C3} U_{DT};$$

$$(8) \quad U_{IPU} = (K_{C3} U_{DT} + \frac{1}{K_{C4}} U_{KPS} + \frac{1}{K_{C3}} U_{BADC} + \frac{1}{K_{C5}} U_K) / (\frac{1}{K_{M3}} + \frac{1}{K_{C3}} + \frac{1}{K_{C5}});$$

$$(9) \quad U_{IPU} = f(U_{KPS}, U_{BADC}, U_K, K_{M3}, K_{C3}, K_{C5});$$

That is U_{IPU} of the model IPU node size $KPS, BADC, K$ sizes in nodes and K_{M3}, K_{C3}, K_{C5} depending on the transmission functions (coefficients) of the model parts and determining on the basis of next equations [2]:

$$(10) \quad U_{IPU}(t) = K U_{ap}(t);$$

$$(11) \quad U_{IPU_{ap}}(t) = K (1 - e^{-\frac{t}{T}}) U_{ap}(t);$$

$$(12) \quad \frac{U_{IPU_{ap}}(t)}{dt} = \omega(t) = \frac{K}{T} e^{-\frac{t}{T}} U_{ap}(t),$$

$$(13) \quad U_{IPU_p}(t) = U_{IPU}(t) \text{Sin} \omega t;$$

$$(14) \quad U_{IPU_{\Sigma}}(t) = U_{IPU_p}(t) + U_{IPU_{ap}}(t);$$

RESULTS OF RESEARCH

The Static characteristics

The static characteristics of PCD given in fig.4. On the basis of static characteristics calculated difference between theoretical (T) and experimental (e) measure or control dates, which equal 3-4%.

Fig.4. The static characteristics of PCD.

$$\delta = \frac{U_{IPU_T} - U_{IPU_e}}{U_{IPU_T}} * 100 = 3\%; \quad (15)$$

An essential functional feature of PCD, which determines the structural and climatic requirements for them, the element base, the power supply system, the ability to store and transmit measurement results, is the type of measurement and control - continuous or periodic [1-2].

Existing standards recommend periodic monitoring of the quantity and quality of electricity at various intervals between subsequent control measurements. So, according to GOST 13109-97, the duration of continuous measurements and control of PCD to monitor compliance with the requirements of this standard determined by 24 hours as mandatory and seven days as recommended. The frequency of power quality control established by this standard is, depending on the type of PQI, from twice a year to once every two years [3].

The Dynamic characteristics

The dynamic characteristics of PCD with different input values ($K=0,9 - 1,1$) and periods of ranging ($T=0,1 - 0,3$), given in fig.4.

1) $K=0.9, T=0.03$

2) $K=1, T=0.03$

3) K=1.1, T=0.03

Fig.4. The dynamic characteristics of PCD

CONCLUSION

1. The graph model for research and design has been developed based on magnetic currents generated by multiphase currents of power sources based on the highly formalized and transparent physical and technical effects, PCD structure involved in the conversion process, which can be exploring static and dynamic characteristics of multiphase sensors of PCD.

2. The graph model of PCD of multiphase current or voltage generated by power sources and the analytical equations, based on the model are adequate to actual linear static outputs, and results of researches showed, that sensitivity of the sensors of PCD can be increased by 3-4%.

3. The output voltage values and change graphs model of PCD depending on arguments and parameters of output voltage are static and dynamic changes in the sensor stabilize after 0.01-0.02 seconds later, when controlling power source connecting to nets of power supply systems.

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